

1 **LRP1b and LRP8 function in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of LRP1b
8 and LRP8 as lineage commitment markers or lineage commitment cooperating factor in embryonic stem
9 cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

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